

Diabetics Prediction using Machine Learning Pipeline

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Abstract: The aim of this paper is to predict whether the person is affected with diabetics based on various factors like age, BMI, diabetics pedigree function, blood pressure. A comparative study of three Machine Learning algorithm, Logistic Regression, Random Forest Classifier and Support Vector Classifier are done in this paper. For that here we use the concept of Machine Learning Pipeline. Logistic Regression is often used for classification and predictive analytics. Support Vector Machine is a model used for both classification and regression. Random Forest Algorithm is a supervised machine learning algorithm which is popular and is used for Classification problems in Machine Learning. The accuracy of the three algorithms in predicting diabetics are calculated and a consistent accuracy is obtained for Random Forest Classifier with 79% for the given dataset. The accuracy of other model is comparatively low. Thus for developing the model, Random Forest Classifier is used. It predicts if the new person (outside the dataset) has/has no diabetics.

Keywords—Machine Learning, Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine(SVM), Random Forest Classifier.

IV. INTRODUCTION

Diabetes, also known as diabetes mellitus (DM), is a chronic condition that develops when the pancreas is unable to produce insulin or when the body is unable to properly utilize the insulin that is produced. Insulin is a hormone made by the pancreas that enables glucose from food to bypass the blood flow into the body's cells, where it can be used as an energy source. Any food containing carbohydrates is broken down into glucose in the blood. glucose builds up in the bloodstream instead of going into the cells. Hyperglycemia, or elevated blood glucose levels, are caused by an inability to make enough insulin or use it properly. When long-time period excessive glucose degrees are related reason damage to the body and failure of numerous organs and tissues. There are three types of diabetics, type 1, type 2, and gestational diabetes (diabetes while pregnant).

In healthcare fields many Machine Learning Techniques are used, like Predictive Modeling, Probabilistic Modeling, etc. Additionally, there also are complicated algorithms for figuring out approaches and styles invisible to the human eye. It facilitates researchers to get new medicine and remedy plans. Logistic regression estimates the opportunity of a occurring, like voted or didn't vote, supported a given dataset of unbiased variables. Support Vector Machine is in

particular used for Classification mechanism in Machine Learning, but it could be used for Classification moreover as Regression mechanism.

V. LITERATURE REVIEW

Machine learning techniques are becoming increasingly useful in the scientific community. Excellent machine learning and deep learning techniques and algorithms have been employed by numerous researchers to predict diabetes. A wide range of sets of rules are available, including the Random Forest Classifier, Decision Tree Classifier, Extra Tree Classifier, Ada Boost set of rules, Perceptron, Linear Discriminant Analysis set of rules, Logistic Regression, K-NN, Gaussian Nave Bayes, Bagging approach, and Gradient Boost Classifier set of rules.

The term "pipeline" is used in this work. The Pipeline is a technique where a number of transforms are sequentially applied before a final estimator. The final estimator just has to implement fit, but intermediate parts of the pipeline must implement fit and transform methods. We have three machine learning algorithms in the pipeline: Random Forest Classifier, Support Vector Machine, and Logistic Regression. As its accuracy is calculated to be higher, Random Forest Classifier determines that it is optimal to use for forecasting purposes. The PIMA Indian dataset is where the dataset came from. Diabetes diagnosis is regarded as a difficult topic for quantitative research because it depends on numerous parameters, each of which varies accordingly.

All of the aforementioned studies present an evaluation of comparative performance amongst various different machine learning methods. These algorithms improved accuracy by pre-processing and cleaning the data, but most of them were more concerned with comparing the performance of various models as a whole than with improving just one. In this study, we even concentrated further on a particular version and investigated approaches that can not only improve accuracy but also improve performance. According to this study, pre- and post-processing of statistics play a significant role in the overall development of the version together with the choice of a set of rules.

VI. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Dataset

The dataset comes from the PIMA Indian Dataset and contains information on female patients who are 21 years of age or older. The used dataset is a CSV file. There are a total of nine features. Each feature is described as follows.

- **Pregnancy:** The number of pregnancies
- **Glucose:** An oral glucose tolerance test requires a plasma glucose concentration of 2 hours.
- **Diastolic blood pressure:** measure of blood pressure (mm Hg).
- **Skin Thickness:** Thickness of the triceps skin fold (mm).
- **Insulin:** 2-hour serum insulin level is the insulin level.
- **Body mass index (BMI):** calculated as weight in kg/(height in m)².
- **The Diabetics Pedigree Function** measures the risk of diabetes based on a family's medical history.
- **Age:** Age in years
- **Outcome:** Class variable (0 if non-diabetic and 1 if diabetic). The target variable is this.

3.2 Data Pre-processing

Real-world data is unstructured, meaning it may contain erroneous or noisy information as well as missing values. If the information is of poor quality, no highly satisfactory results can be obtained. To obtain highly satisfactory results, the records must be preprocessed [2]. The data is preprocessed using cleaning, integration, transformation, reduction, and discretization. It is crucial to improve the data's suitability for time, cost, and quality-sensitive data mining and evaluation.

3.3 Data Cleaning

It is the process of filling the missing numbers as well as removing 0 values and noisy statistics are all parts of data cleansing. Noisy data contains outliers that should be removed to eliminate anomalies. In our dataset, there are a few 0 values for blood pressure, pores and skin thickness, insulin, and BML. As a result, the mean value of that characteristic has been substituted for each of the 0 values. The diversity of attributes in a dataset can be reduced through the use of data reduction. The significant attribute evaluation technique was used to extract significant attributes from a complete dataset. Age, diastolic blood pressure, BMI, glucose, and BMI were all sizable characteristics in the sample.

3.4 Splitting of Dataset

The complete dataset is divided into a training dataset and a test dataset after pre-processing and data cleaning. The remaining 20% of the data are utilized for testing, and the remaining 80% are used for training. The relevant data

variable is used to hold the training and test data, which is then used for future prediction.

3.5 Find accuracy

Next accuracy of each technique is evaluated. That is, examined the training score and test score of three algorithms and compared the average of each algorithm. Thus, we go forward with the algorithm having the greatest accuracy to build the model

Figure.1 shows the model of the Diabetics Prediction Model (flowchart). Model include the selection of dataset, the processing of data and data cleaning. That processed data will be split to form test dataset and training dataset. After training process, find the accuracy of the model with the given dataset[2] and model is selected. By using that model we predict the output that is, the person is diabetic or not.

Fig.1. Flow Chart for the Diabetics Model Prediction

The heat map showed in Fig. 2, shows the correlation between the attributes of Dataset. Correlation heat map can be used to find potential relationships between variables and to understand the strength of these relationships. The darker colors represent more correlation and the lighter colors

Fig.2 Heatmap showing the correlation between the features of Dataset

3.4 Modeling

Three models were used in this paper, and most accurate model is used for the prediction of diabetes. They are

3.4.1 Logistic Regression

Logistic regression aims to solve classification problems. It does this by predicting categorical outcomes, unlike linear regression that predicts a continuous outcome. In the simplest case, there are two outcomes, which is called binomial

3.2.2 Support Vector Classifier

A supervised learning approach called Support Vector Machine, or SVM, is used to solve Classification and Regression issues. The goal of the SVM is to establish the optimal decision boundary or line that can divide the n-dimensional space into classes, allowing us to quickly classify fresh data points. A hyper plane is the name given to this optimal boundary. The SVC algorithm selects the extreme points or vectors known as support vectors that aid in generating the hyper plane.

3.4.3 Random Forest Classifier

The Random Forest(RF) technique, which combines tree predictors, is a versatile, quick, and easy machine learning approach. Most of the time, the RF yields results that are sufficient. Additionally, it can handle a variety of data, including numerical, categorical and nominal data. Both classification and regression have made use of it. Machine learning's main duty is classification. It is simple to investigate the fact that random trees overlap in random forests. The over fitting problem is also resolved by this approach.

A plot illustrating the patients with and without diabetes in the dataset is shown in Fig. 3. It is clear from the bar graph that there are 250 people without diabetes and 500 people

with diabetes. This is accomplished by using the dataset's outcome field.

Fig.3. Count of Patients with and without diabetics

The calculated train accuracy and test accuracy is shown in Fig.4 and Fig.5

```
for i,model in enumerate(pipelines):
    print("{} Train Accuracy:{}".format(pipe_dict[i],model.score(X_train,y_train)*100))
```

Logistic Regression Train Accuracy:77.0358306188925
Support Vector Classifier Train Accuracy:82.41042345276874
Random Forest Classifier Train Accuracy:78.99022801302932

Fig.4 Training Accuracy

```
for i,model in enumerate(pipelines):
    print("{} Test Accuracy:{}".format(pipe_dict[i],model.score(X_test,y_test)*100))
```

Logistic Regression Test Accuracy:76.62337662337663
Support Vector Classifier Test Accuracy:73.37662337662337
Random Forest Classifier Test Accuracy:81.16883116883116

Fig.5 Test Accuracy

VII. RESULTS

A bar plot illustrating the patients with and without diabetes in the dataset is shown in Fig. 3. It is clear from the bar graph that there are 250 people without diabetes and 500 people with diabetes. This is accomplished by using the dataset's outcome field.

Table 1

Method	Accuracy	
	Training	Testing
Logistic Regression	77.03%	76.62%
Support Vector Machine	82.41%	73.37%
Random Forest Classifier	79.31%	78.57%

We investigate the Random Forest Classifier algorithm from Table 1 since it has a higher degree of accuracy. It is so because using the mean of train and test accuracy yields a mean accuracy of 79% for the dataset in consideration, compared to 77% and 78% for logistic regression and 78% for support vector machines, respectively. Therefore, diabetics are predicted using the Random Forest Classifier.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Diabetes is a relatively prevalent chronic condition that is assessed with the aid of a diagnostic test. They have first examined the hourly rates of serum and plasma glucose. Fasting blood glucose levels that are higher than recommended have historically been part of the diabetes diagnosis. A other element, such as body mass index, was also crucial in the diagnosing process. When a woman has a prior pregnancy, her risk of diabetes during pregnancy is higher. The diabetes dataset for Pima Indians was used.

Data preprocessing is one crucial component. It is necessary to eliminate redundant and null values in order to increase efficiency. Throughout this study, we have shown that characteristic selection plays an important part in increasing accuracy and decreasing runtime. Random Forest has been shown to be one of the most ecologically friendly algorithms for creating prediction models. The accuracy of the model now depends on a number of parameters in addition to the chosen rules. By selecting Random Forest Classifier, the version changes. That revised version includes the diabetics' forecast. The version will forecast the outcome once it has received new data.

IX. FUTURE WORK

Nowadays, machine learning is applied in practically all industries. Its application in the medical field has the potential to significantly enhance healthcare. We employ a variety of features, including age, BMI, the function of the diabetes ancestry, insulin, blood pressure, and other factors. These elements play a significant role in the prediction of diabetes. We can take these characteristics into account and create a diet recommendation system as future work. The changes of the components in the dataset we used here are significantly influenced by our eating behaviors.

X. REFERENCES

[1]<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666990021000318>

[2] M. Rady, K. Moussa, M. Mostafa, A. Elbasry, Z. Ezzat, and W. Medhat, "Diabetes Prediction Using Machine Learning: A Comparative Study,"

[3]PIMA Indian Dataset, 2021 <https://www.kaggle.com/uciml/pima-indians-diabetes-database>.

[4] National Institute of Diabetes and Kidney Diseases, 2021 <https://www.niddk.nih.gov/health-information/diabetes>

[5]From google: <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/support-vector-machine-algorithm/>

[6] Temurtas H, Yumusak N, Temurtas F (2009) A comparative study on diabetes disease diagnosis using neural networks. Expert Syst Appl 36(4):8610–8615